

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION PLAN INCLUDING EDITORIAL CALENDAR TEMPLATE

Deliverable 11.2

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Abstract

The purpose of this Communication & Dissemination Plan (CDP) is to create and implement a robust framework to guide communication, visualisation, and dissemination activities throughout the project. This document will aid in the successful execution of the project, publication of its results, and maximising its impact on policy and management.

This document is developed as part of the EXPECT project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Research and Innovation programme, under the Grant Agreement number 101137656.

The communication and dissemination activities are coordinated in close collaboration with the beneficiaries of the EXPECT project.

Arctik will lay the foundation for communication and dissemination activities (WP11, and will boost the communication and dissemination of the project outcomes, future exploitation and capacity building (WP12).

The initial package of communication and dissemination materials, tools and plan will contribute to the overall promotion and dissemination of the project's results, resources, and outputs to target audiences.

The CDP will include defining the target audiences (such as climate scientists, policymakers, sister projects, and media) and mapping key stakeholders and publications for outreach. Additionally, a proposal for an editorial calendar is presented to ensure the regular publication of timely and high-quality content.

This plan will be updated throughout the project, so that all communication and dissemination actions are as effective as possible. Internal annual reports and the project periodic reports in M18 and M36 will compile and evaluate the impact of all communication activities with D12.1. Impact evaluation of communication, dissemination activities and capacity building, and the plan will be updated accordingly.

1. Introduction

The following document outlines the communication and dissemination plan for EXPECT's duration. The communication and dissemination activities are coordinated in close collaboration with the consortium and incorporate inputs from all other project partners.

Arctik is responsible for overseeing the entire communication and dissemination plan, with the official deadline for the deliverable set for M6 (September 2024).

Clear and measurable objectives for communication and dissemination are defined within this plan. These objectives will be reviewed through internal annual reports and the project periodic reports in M18 and M36, and activities will be monitored and evaluated using various key performance indicators. The plan also addresses key challenges and proposes solutions.

This CDP is aimed to create and implement an effective framework to guide communication and dissemination activities throughout the project. This approach will ensure the project's successful execution and maximise its impact. The evaluation of the impact of all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will be presented with a report at the end of the project with D12.1.

The CDP outlines target groups and identifies relevant communication channels and tools. It will utilise both digital and non-digital methods, including an interactive website, a X and a LinkedIn social media account, and a mix of offline activities such as videos and events.

All communication and dissemination activities detailed in this report will comply with the Data Management Plan (D13.2) and the Guidelines for effective project implementation, quality and risk management which are reported in the Project Handbook (D13.1).

1.1 Contributions from consortium members

Even though Arctik is responsible for designing and executing the CDP, the involvement of consortium members is essential for its success. This plan specifies the timing and methods for team members to communicate about and share the project's outcomes. The opportunities are summarised in the list below:

- **Using EXPECT materials and templates:** The consortium partners are provided with various templates and communication materials that align with the project's visual identity. Members are encouraged to use these resources, which are accessible on the project's Wiki.
- **Communicating on their own social media profiles:** All consortium partners are encouraged to share updates about their contributions to the project on their individual X or LinkedIn accounts and tag the @EXPECT_Project X and @EXPECT Project LinkedIn handles and for easier reposting.

- **Keeping Arctik informed:** Consortium members will notify Arctik of any activities that could serve as communication or dissemination, such as participating in external conferences and events or publications. This can be done by sending a brief email to expect_communication@bsc.es.
- **Contributing to communication and dissemination reporting:** Consortium members are responsible for documenting their activities in the Participants Portal.
- **Contributing to mappings:** Consortium members will contribute to mapping relevant stakeholders, external events, scientific publications, and media. This can be accomplished by adding information to the dedicated shared Google spreadsheet.
- **Identifying synergies:** The consortium is encouraged to inform Arctik about any potential synergies and opportunities for knowledge exchange with external initiatives or projects via email at expect_communication@bsc.es.

1.2 Contributions from Multipliers

Multipliers are initiatives or actors already connected with our target audiences. As part of our communication plan, we will identify and reach out to these multipliers, sharing updates with them as the project progresses. They will be asked to re-share our updates on their newsletters, social media or media which will help us to grow our audience.

Multipliers are particularly crucial for projects with shorter timeframes (less than 10 years) since becoming recognised as a key player takes time. These relationships will be mutually beneficial, as we will involve these stakeholders in various activities, such as webinars or external events, where appropriate.

Additionally, we will build on existing initiatives and events to broaden the impact of our communication and dissemination efforts. The Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change Webinar series (by the EPESC-LHA), for example, will be a suitable medium to reach large parts of the interested climate science community.

Under the task 13.2: Project Clustering (M1-M18), led by BSC, EXPECT will leverage sister projects, media, and other related initiatives as amplifiers, and consider, for example, the Researchers Communication Community established under the ESM2025 project.

Synergies to help with the efficient dissemination and exploitation in terms of training activities will include contributions to online courses (e.g. the MOOC on ML in Weather & Climate organised by ECMWF) and summer schools (e.g. the NCAS Climate Modelling Summer School).

2. General objectives

The main objective of EXPECT is to enable trustworthy assessments and predictions of regional climate change, including extremes, by developing a prototype operational capability for integrated attribution and prediction of climate. We also promote collaboration and knowledge-sharing among international research communities, strengthening global efforts to manage and adapt to climate change impacts.

Effective communication is pivotal to achieving the general objective of the project, by ensuring that project findings reach pertinent audiences and have a sustained impact beyond the project's duration.

This communication and dissemination plan aims to outline **key messages, target audiences, stakeholders, communication tools, channels, resources**, and planned **activities** to promote the project and its outcomes. The plan will evolve throughout the project to maximise the effectiveness of each communication and dissemination effort.

An editorial calendar proposal is also developed to ensure regular publication of timely and high-quality content. This calendar will be **updated regularly as communication needs and outcomes evolve**.

This document will serve as a guide throughout the project, facilitating consistent messaging and ensuring that outputs are tailored to meet the needs of target audiences. For example, it will ensure the timely dissemination of fact sheets to policymakers.

The plan is based on **two core pillars: communication and dissemination**, each with specific objectives contributing to the project's success. They will ensure that information is shared promptly and effectively with relevant internal and external stakeholders, using appropriate communication tools.

Figure 1 – Strategic pillars: communication and dissemination.

2.1 Communication – Promoting action and results

“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”¹

2.1.1 General communication goals

While the overall communication goal of EXPECT is to inform, promote and communicate the project’s activities and results, this objective can be further broken down as follows:

- Raising awareness on advanced climate science towards integrated attribution and prediction to support climate adaptation strategies for a resilient society.
- Showcase project outcomes using editorial content on the website, social media; and events, including tracking impact and reporting yearly on communication and dissemination activities.
- Building awareness of the EXPECT project objectives using a wide variety of communication and aggregation tools to reach as many stakeholders as possible.
- Create and update communication materials such as videos and science explainers to break down key messages for target audiences.
- Organise, promote and perform capacity building activities to engage the wider climate science community.

2.1.2 Specific communication goals

The communication and dissemination plan will also set specific goals based on the thematic overall goals (O1-O7) of the project:

- Actively communicate and disseminate the integrated attribution, prediction and projection results to stakeholders and decision-makers (O7).
- Raise awareness about the benefits of using combined novel ways state-of-the-art (SoA) EO data and climate simulations to enhance regional climate forecasts and inform better decision-making (*corresponding to O1*).
- Educate the climate science and wider impacts communities, policymakers, and decision-makers on how natural and human-induced factors, atmospheric circulation, and local processes interact to influence European climate and its summertime extremes (*corresponding to O2*).
- Enhance the understanding on the drivers of European heatwaves, droughts and persistent extreme precipitation events (*corresponding to O3*).
- Translate the complexities of distributed analytics across a variety of large data from observations and simulations held in different repositories into accessible information for the public (*corresponding to O4*).

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1#>

2.2 Dissemination – Making the results public

Dissemination is “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”²

Communication involves promoting the project through targeted information to various audiences, whereas dissemination of results means making those results public through suitable channels. Dissemination of results cannot replace communication activities (or vice-versa).

The dissemination activities within EXPECT will be used to inform the target audiences and stakeholders about the project progress and results with the aim to enhance the uptake of the research.

2.2.1 Dissemination goals

The goal of the dissemination activities is to share research findings with the stakeholders, policymakers and the wider target audience.

- Disseminate the EXPECT's research results, products, and services as well as their benefits to all target groups, and to demonstrate the impact of European funded research projects.
- Organise and attend events with related stakeholders to disseminate scientific outcomes.
- Fostering and strengthening synergies and engagement across climate-related practitioners, decision-makers, and policymakers.
- Organise, promote and perform capacity-building activities to engage the wider climate science community with tools and data developed within the project.

Due to the project's strong emphasis on fundamental research and the need to inform international climate assessments like the IPCC, the prompt publication of the research results in the peer-reviewed literature is a key priority for disseminating the outcomes of EXPECT.

Additionally, research results will be shared at external events, including online and onsite conferences. This will enhance the project's visibility and foster new connections with other relevant projects and researchers in the field. For more details, see section 5.2.4: External events, conferences, and workshops.

3. Methodology

Answering the question “how?”, this section of the communication plan outlines three interconnected steps that will organise communication activities throughout the

² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1#>

project's duration, facilitate audience engagement, and harmonise internal and external communications.

3.1 Raising awareness and the marketing funnel

Generally, audiences need time to become familiar with a new project. It's uncommon for someone to immediately adopt a project's recommendations or outputs after their first interaction. Trust and use of a project's outputs are often built through repeated interactions over time.

Thus, all major communication actions will be structured around the *marketing funnel* principle shown in figure 2. This funnel illustrates the journey an audience member takes from first hearing about EXPECT to *converting*, by for example taking the desired action. It tries to have audience members move through the steps of *awareness*, *consideration*, and *decision* to *conversion*:

- **awareness** – an audience member first comes into contact with EXPECT on social media, during an event or in multiplier communication, and takes a superficial interest.
- **consideration** – an audience member has taken an interest in EXPECT and starts engaging more with its content and starts consuming more in-depth content. This can mean that they follow the project on social media, consume our editorial or video content or deliberately attend one of our events.
- **decision** – an audience member starts using EXPECT outputs and recommendations.
- **conversion/advocacy** – once an audience member converts (conversion), they become an advocate. In this role, they can help boost or multiply our message or influence others.

It is crucial to raise awareness and engage with as many target groups and stakeholders as possible at the onset of the project, as the effectiveness of various communication tools depends on stakeholder involvement. These tools include:

- events (both internal and external),
- social media,
- website and its editorial content.

An audience does not progress through the funnel uniformly. At the starting point, different audience members are at different places in the funnel. Some of them are, for instance, already aware of the goals of EXPECT through previous interactions with the consortium partners' work and, therefore, prepared to consider or decide at an early stage. The conversion process will also have different speeds depending on an audience member's pre-existing involvement with the topics EXPECT is dealing with.

Figure 2 – Marketing funnel

These audience members will be more easily 'converted' than, for instance, those whose approach solely focuses on one aspect of the project.

As such, we will ensure that our content is balanced to address target groups and stakeholders at various stages of the funnel. This involves delivering more targeted content to keep more engaged, mature audience members interested, while also offering entry-level, bite-sized content to help new audience members begin progressing through the funnel. Without this balance, audience growth may stagnate as the initial segments of the funnel become depleted.

3.2 Engagement triangle

The strategic approach of the engagement triangle helps to structure communication activities over time. While the marketing funnel helps to structure who should be targeted by the content, the engagement triangle outlines which types of content are needed for the different parts of the funnel.

Figure 3 – Engagement triangle

The triangle, as shown in figure 3, has proven effective and facilitates placing different communication activities on a timeline following the different layers of the triangle leading to an effective engagement of target audiences, both internal and external. It forms the basis for an effective process to secure target-oriented communication as

well as for large-spectrum communication. On top of the pyramid, there is the campaign. A campaign serves to attract new audience members. Typically, a campaign will be organised twice a year, depending on the project outputs.

The second level of the engagement triangle, **top-topical** communication, refers to engagements via external hooks such as a new climate policy or large event which creates a lot of buzz. On average, a top-topical communication action will be organised monthly or every two months.

To maintain the steady relationship over time, we will use a fixed **format** to enhance loyalty among audience members, which is to be done often and consistently. An example for such communication activities could be news items.

At the bottom of the pyramid, there is the flow. This refers to the daily interaction with audience members via social media and via email or through an active X account and through LinkedIn posts by individual consortium members.

3.3 Know | Like | Trust: three cumulative steps

To facilitate the uptake of the EXPECT findings, Arctic proposes to follow a three-step approach. This approach, known to the world of sales and marketing, has also proven effectiveness for communication activities.

Communication activities will follow the **“know – like – trust” approach**. This approach means people will engage and do business with people they will first get to know, then like and finally trust.

Figure 4 - The « know – like – trust » approach

3.3.1 A communication that “catches the eye” | KNOW

To increase awareness of the project findings and encourage their adoption, the communication team must first inform target audiences about the EXPECT project. An appealing visual identity will ensure consistency in communication and attract attention, boosting the project's recognition. In fact, the first thing by which many people will get to know the project is by the visual identity. Detailed information on the EXPECT's visual identity can be found in section 5.1.1 Visual Identity.

3.3.2 Provide attractive information | LIKE

Once our target groups have been introduced to EXPECT, we will offer more detailed information about the project and its anticipated outcomes. At this stage, the target audience will begin to like the project. This can be achieved through an article, a video, a recorded interview, an infographic, or similar mediums. To engage people effectively, the angle of the story is crucial.

3.3.3 Get deeper | TRUST

At this stage, the target is seriously interested and must be fed with detailed, substantive information. Scientific articles and proof points are crucial here, as well as the consortium participation at workshops and events. The goal is to prompt the audience to act, so messages will include calls to action (CTAs) such as "visit our website" or "meet us at event X" where appropriate. This will encourage the audience to engage with the project and, in some cases, provide their contact details.

4. Target audiences, messages, and synergies

The definition of target audiences is a key resource for us to ensure EXPECT's messages reach the appropriate audiences. At the proposal stage, nine target groups were identified; these are detailed below, along with attributed messaging for every audience group.

Potential synergies with external projects and initiatives, including other Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe projects, are being identified and will be detailed in the Milestones 13, 14 and 15.

Contact details of target groups or stakeholders will not be uploaded on the Wiki for data protection reasons. Consortium members who have relevant contacts in a particular area will leverage their networks to reach the target groups or stakeholders.

4.1 Target groups

The target groups for the communication and dissemination activities of EXPECT are:

- **Climate and Data science community:** researchers, scientists, and academics specialising in climate change, its impacts, and mitigation strategies, along with professionals and experts in data analysis, machine learning, and data-driven approaches.
- **Wider research community concerned with climate impacts:** Including interdisciplinary researchers, environmental scientists, and social scientists studying various aspects of climate change and its societal impacts.
- **Policymakers and decision-makers concerned with risk assessment:** Government officials, policymakers, and advisors, as well as leaders in various sectors such as public administration, business, and NGOs, who are involved in assessing, mitigating, and making decisions based on climate-related risks through policy, regulation, and strategic planning.
- **Consortium partners, European Commission's projects and Policy Officers:** diverse organisations, academic institutions, research bodies, and private companies that collaborate on joint projects; other initiatives and programs that are funded and overseen by the European Commission with the aim of tackling climate change and enhancing resilience across Europe; and professionals who work within governmental and intergovernmental organisations.
- **Funding agencies:** European entities providing financial support for research, projects, and initiatives related to climate science, adaptation, and mitigation.
- **Climate services community:** Organisations, agencies, and private sector entities offering a range of climate-related services and products. This includes services such as climate forecasting, adaptation strategies, and risk management solutions, as well as products related to climate risk management, including insurance, agricultural technologies, and renewable energy solutions.
- **Data providers and data centres:** Organisations, institutions, and facilities responsible for collecting, processing, storing, managing, and distributing large volumes of climate and environmental data for research and decision-making purposes.

- **Sister projects and related projects and initiatives:** Other research projects, initiatives, or collaborations with synergies or overlaps in objectives and outcomes related to climate science and adaptation.
- **Media:** Journalists, editors, and media outlets interested in reporting on climate science, policy developments, and related issues to raise public awareness and understanding.

4.2 Messaging per target audience

To effectively connect with the identified target audience, it is crucial for the EXPECT project to deeply understand their unique needs, interests, and the messaging that will resonate with them. By identifying who they are, what drives their interest, and what information they seek, the communication and dissemination plan will be tailored and adapted accordingly.

- All project partners have actively contributed to the EXPECT stakeholder mapping and the development of key messages by addressing the following questions:
- What would you say to the climate scientists / policy makers / sister projects / media / general public in relation with EXPECT?
- Why is it interesting and important for a broader public?
- Which climate scientists / policy makers / sister projects / media could be interested in this topic?
- Do you already have contacts with climate scientists / policy makers / sister projects / media within your organisation? Who in your organisation/network could help?

The table on the subsequent pages is an example on how to connect these elements for each specific target group. These messages will evolve and be refined as the project advances and the understanding of the EXPECT target audiences deepens.

Table 1 - Messaging per target audience

Target audiences - Who	Why	What (messages)	How (Tools and channels)
Climate and Data science community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educate the climate science and data science communities on how natural and human-induced factors, atmospheric circulation, and local processes interact to influence European climate and its summertime extremes. Enhance the understanding on the drivers of European Enhance the understanding of the drivers of European heatwaves, droughts and persistent extreme precipitation events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is EXPECT? Why is the research done under EXPECT important? Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? What solutions are we aiming to find? Why is it important to improve the accuracy of regional climate predictions? How can advanced data analysis and machine learning enhance climate predictions? Why is collaboration crucial for addressing discrepancies between climate models and observations? What challenges arise in predicting extreme climate events, and how can they be overcome? How can new tools and high-resolution models increase the reliability of climate forecasts? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social media: LinkedIn & X Online campaigns Printed marketing materials Digital marketing materials Organisation of workshops Participation at events & conferences Multipliers & sister projects Media relations EC channels & tools
Wider research community concerned with climate impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educate the wider research community concerned with climate impacts on how natural and human-induced factors, atmospheric circulation, and local processes interact to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is EXPECT? Why is the research done under EXPECT important? Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? What solutions are we aiming to find? Why is it essential for climate impact research to be interdisciplinary? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social media: LinkedIn & X Online campaigns Printed marketing materials Digital marketing materials

	<p>influence European climate and its summertime extremes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translate the complexities of distributed analytics across a variety of large data from observations and simulations held in different repositories into accessible information for the public. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can integrating social, environmental, and climate sciences improve our understanding of climate change? • What are the societal impacts of regional climate change that need attention? • Why are comprehensive strategies necessary for enhancing resilience and adaptation to climate change? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of workshops • Participation at events & conferences • Multipliers & sister projects • Media relations • EC channels & tools
<p>Policy-makers and decision-makers concerned with risk assessment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate the policymakers, and decision-makers on how natural and human-induced factors, atmospheric circulation, and local processes interact to influence European climate and its summertime extremes. • Actively communicate and disseminate the integrated attribution, prediction and projection results to policymakers and decision-makers. • Raise awareness about the benefits of using combined novel ways state-of-the-art EO data and climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • Why is the research done under EXPECT important? • Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? • How can regional climate predictions inform policy and decision-making? • Why is reliable climate data crucial for risk assessment and strategic planning? • What role does policy play in mitigating climate risks and enhancing community resilience? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media: LinkedIn & X • Online campaigns • Printed marketing materials • Digital marketing materials • Policy materials • Participation at events & conferences • Media relations • EC channels & tools

	<p>simulations to enhance regional climate forecasts and inform better decision-making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase awareness and support development of future policies and regulation 		
<p>Consortium partners, European Commission's projects and Policy Officers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the understanding on the drivers of European heatwaves, droughts and persistent extreme precipitation events. • Translate the complexities of distributed analytics across a variety of large data from observations and simulations held in different repositories into accessible information for the public. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? • What solutions are we aiming to find? • Why is collaboration essential in tackling climate change across Europe? • How does the project align with European Commission initiatives? • What is the importance of joint efforts in enhancing resilience to climate change in Europe? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media: LinkedIn & X • Online campaigns • Printed marketing materials • Digital marketing materials • Policy materials • Organisation of workshops • Participation at events & conferences • Multipliers & sister projects • EC channels & tools
<p>Funding agencies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness about the benefits of using combined novel ways state-of-the-art 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • Why is the research done under EXPECT important? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media: LinkedIn & X

	<p>EO data and climate simulations to enhance regional climate forecasts and inform better decision-making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw attention to the remaining knowledge and technology gaps that we need to address in order to improve our capability to address the drivers of European heatwaves, droughts and persistent extreme precipitation events. • Shed light on the complementary research that is needed to advance the understanding of climate variability and change, and its impacts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? • What potential advancements in climate science does the project offer? • How can the project benefit society? • Why is financial support crucial for developing innovative solutions for climate adaptation and mitigation? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online campaigns • Printed marketing materials • Digital marketing materials • Policy materials • Organisation of workshops • Participation at events & conferences • EC channels & tools
<p>Climate services community / Data providers and data centres</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translate the complexities of distributed analytics across a variety of large data from observations and simulations held in different repositories into accessible information, with a focus on providing specific, actionable methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • What can EXPECT do for you? • Why is the research done under EXPECT important? • Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? • What are the practical applications of regional climate predictions for climate services? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media: LinkedIn & X • Online campaigns • Printed marketing materials

	<p>tailored to the needs of data centres and climate services.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness about the benefits of using combined novel ways state-of-the-art EO data and climate simulations to enhance regional climate forecasts and inform better decision-making • Promote knowledge of new methods can improve the accuracy and reliability of climate forecasts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can products and strategies for climate risk management, such as forecasting, adaptation, and renewable energy solutions, be developed? • Why is high-quality data important for improving regional climate predictions? • How can collaboration in data collection, processing, and sharing support climate research and decision-making? • What new methods can enhance the accuracy and reliability of climate forecasts? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital marketing materials • Participation at events & conferences • Media relations
<p>Sister projects and related projects and initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and explore synergies and potential collaborations with other projects and initiatives, and assess how shared objectives can enhance collaboration and improve outcomes in achieving common goals. • Raise awareness about the benefits of using combined novel ways state-of-the-art EO data and climate simulations to enhance regional climate forecasts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • What can EXPECT do for you? • Why is the research done under EXPECT important? • What solutions are we aiming to find? • Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? • What synergies and potential collaborations exist with other projects and initiatives? • How can shared objectives enhance the benefits of working together to achieve common goals? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media: LinkedIn & X • Online campaigns • Printed marketing materials • Digital marketing materials • Participation at events & conferences

	<p>and inform better decision-making</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multipliers & sister projects • Media relations • EC channels & tools • Organisation of workshops
<p>General public and media</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build awareness of the EXPECT project objectives using a wide variety of communication and aggregation tools to reach as many citizens as possible. • Translate the complexities of climate variability and change, and associated extreme events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • Why is the research done under EXPECT important? • Who are the people behind EXPECT? • Why are regional climate predictions important, and what are their societal impacts? • What role does the media play in raising public awareness and understanding of climate science and policy developments? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media: LinkedIn & X • Online campaigns • Printed marketing materials • Digital marketing materials • Participation at events & conferences • Media relations

5. Tools and channels

Table 2 – Tools and channels per target audiences

Tools & channels (How)	Climate and Data science community	Wider research community concerned with climate impacts	Policymakers and decision-makers concerned with risk assessment	Consortium partners, European Commission's projects and Policy Officers	Funding agencies	Climate services community / Data providers and data centres	Sister projects and related projects and initiatives	General public & media
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media: LinkedIn & X	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Online campaigns	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
External newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
Printed marketing materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Digital marketing materials	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Policy materials			✓	✓	✓			
Organisation of workshops	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Participation at events & conferences	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multipliers & sister projects	✓	✓		✓			✓	
Media relations	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
EC channels & tools	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

The tools and channels marked with a check mark (✓) will be used to reach each target group.

In this section, communication and dissemination tools and channels will be detailed:

5.1 Owned tools and channels

The EXPECT consortium will the owned channels and tools described in detail below. The primary advantage is that this allows the consortium to manage the tone, voice, and content published.

It is important to note that these channels and tools are newly established and still need to develop an audience. Consequently, the current plan also incorporates multiplier tools and channels outlined in section 4.2. These are well-established platforms owned by external parties with audiences that overlap with those of the project.

5.1.1 Visual identity

To raise awareness about the EXPECT project, its mission, research, products, and services should be made known. Creating attractive visuals and a coherent visual identity is a first step towards achieving this objective. It provides consistency in the communication, and it helps to attract the attention from the audience.

As the visual identity is usually the first thing many people will associate the EXPECT project with, the layout and colours associated with this identity will be applied to all related project materials and publications (e.g. website, social media, reports, flyers, etc.) and the designs in general will be clean, modern, and image-based, using images and icons, to tell the story of the project at a glance.

The logo, templates and brand guidelines were made available to the consortium in Month 3 as part of the **Deliverable 11.1 Visual identity**. Additional updates to these materials will be done **under WP12**.

Logo and colours

The logo has been created taking the objective and the vision of the project into consideration. The EXPECT logo is an artistic interpretation of the circumglobal Rossby Wave Patterns over the Northern hemisphere extra-tropics, capturing the undulating nature of these atmospheric waves.

This logo is intended for use on all documents, reports, deliverables and other material produced in the project. Thus, it has been designed for versatility, ensuring a professional and consistent look across all documents, reports, deliverables, and other project materials.

Figure 5 – EXPECT logo

For optimal visibility, there are versions of the logo tailored for both light and dark backgrounds. Below there are examples of good and incorrect logo usage.

Additionally, an icon version of the logo is available for use in space-constrained cases, ensuring brand recognition even in minimal contexts like social media profiles.

EXPECT's colour palette was developed based on the colour scheme developed for the project proposal, in order to ensure consistency. The colour palette for EXPECT features primary colours of dark blue, light blue, and green. These will be complemented by secondary colours—red, yellow, purple, turquoise, pink, and bright green— to add vibrancy and flexibility, ensuring a consistent and dynamic brand presence across all materials.

Figure 6 – EXPECT primary colours

Figure 7 – EXPECT secondary colours

The visual identity respects the EC guidelines for research projects: All communication related to the project **must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag and funding statement** and include the following disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

For instance, since **X** has a 160-character limit for profile information, we will use the following sentence as a biography, as a pinned tweet/post or in the profile banner:

This project receives funding from the European Union #HorizonEU Research and Innovation Programme. Any related tweets reflect only the views of the project owner.

Figure 8 - Use of the EU emblem

As the EXPECT project is also funded by the Government of Canada through the New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF) and the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee via UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), all project templates will include the following disclaimer:

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

The UK participation in the project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee, and Canadian participation in the EXPECT project draws upon research supported by the Government of Canada's New Frontiers in Research Fund (NFRF).

Figure 9 - Example of the acknowledgements of funding

For designs with limited space, the EU emblem will be displayed alongside the logos of the Government of Canada and UK Research and Innovation.

Tagline

Complementary to the full name of the project, Towards an Integrated Capability to Explain and Predict Regional Climate Changes, and its abbreviation, EXPECT, **a short and easily understandable tagline** has been created: "Explaining and Predicting Climate Changes and Extremes".

This tagline will be used on the project website and other communication resources such as flyers, brochures, presentations and social media banners.

The tagline was agreed on after consultations with the project coordinator.

Templates

To ensure that the project partners can easily use the visual identity throughout the project life cycle, we have produced a set of templates:

- Word documents (deliverable format, report format, milestone format and minutes format)
- PowerPoint template
- Social media visual templates, in easy-to-use Canva format
- Template for posters for scientific conferences and events

5.1.2 Flyer

With the purpose of explaining and adding value to scientific results for ease of understanding, an EXPECT project flyer will be developed (MS11.2). This flyer will offer a simple, comprehensive overview of the project, making it easy to distribute and understand.

This flyer will provide potential stakeholders or multipliers with an understanding of the project's goals and outcomes. It will feature a description of the project, including an overview of the methods, and solutions, and other resources such as infographics will be explored.

In accordance with the European Commission's policies, printed materials will be minimised. Therefore, the flyer will be hosted on the website and primarily available online for audiences to download. Physical copies may be printed in limited quantities for specific events where necessary.

5.1.3 Website

Under the web domain www.expect-project.eu, a user-friendly and responsive project website will be launched by M6 (MS11.1). This website will serve as the main information point and will present the project and the expected outcomes, as well as all the partners involved.

In addition, the site will provide direct access to the resources and materials produced within the project and will be the entry point to the web platform for code and data sharing developed in WP12.

Arctik leads the website creation, development and maintenance. To attract and retain the interest of its target audiences, the website will be regularly updated with new content based on research and activities conducted across WPs. The updates to the website form part of the editorial work in WP12.

The website's structure will be regularly reviewed and updated as the project progresses. The content development for the website is based on a progressive and interactive process, involving contributions from all partners.

Type of content on website

The EXPECT website will contain the following types of content:

- A project statement
- A brief description for the homepage
- An alternative way to describe the project on the homepage using "why, what, where"
- A description of the project on the "About EXPECT" page
- The consortium
- A Library / Resources (incl. press releases, scientific publications, videos, policy briefings, etc.)
- News pieces/short articles on the website to profile young researchers in the project, interviews with WP Leaders, summary reports of key findings, etc.

- Public deliverables
- Contact

The consortium will regularly be encouraged to share for publication:

- Updates on their activities for EXPECT
- Any EXPECT related news that they see fit (presentation of activities, presentation of reports, participation in events, speeches, etc.)

A detailed content strategy can be found in section 6.

Open data science platform

A dedicated 'data science platform' will be created and integrated with the project website (D12.2) as part of the dissemination and exploitation-related activities that will focus on the promotion of capacity-building for the climate science community and young researchers, ensuring the impact of the project beyond the project cycle and reaching a wide community of specialists.

Led by BSC, the goal of this open data science platform will be, as its name indicates, to promote open science and ensure reproducibility and build data science capacities in the wider community. EXPECT also focuses on ensuring the availability, usability, and reproducibility of developed methods and tools through this open data science platform, promoting wide adoption.

The platform will host a database of standardised benchmarks, evaluation protocols, source codes, and pre-trained ML models. This platform will engage at least 50 researchers. These components will provide a centralised location for researchers and practitioners to access and replicate the benchmark datasets and ML models developed within the project.

5.1.4 Videos

Adding value to scientific results for ease of understanding and aiming to break down key messages for target audiences, project videos will be created.

On average, one video will be produced per year, in addition to the introductory video, leading to **five videos** in total.

- During year 1, an **introductory video** will be created using stock footage, images, illustrations, or animations. This general video will be produced early in the project to introduce EXPECT and illustrate the main objectives of the project. This video can be, for example, shared with different groups of stakeholders to allow an easier familiarisation with EXPECT, or played at different events.
- During the years 1-4, other four videos are foreseen. These videos will depend on the project results and will be explained in more details in the revisions of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, planned in Month 18 and Month 36. These videos can be developed as science explainer content in video format.

5.1.5 Science explainers

Led by BSC and with the contribution of ARCTIK and in collaboration with the scientists, a series of science explainers will be created for the broader research community and decision-makers (M6-48).

The objective of these science explainers is to **bring the scientific process** (including key research questions and main motivations) **closer to other researchers and decision-makers** and, hence, improve understanding of and trust in climate science.

Science explainers will provide access to information and insights typically unavailable outside the consortium, such as the process of moving from a research idea to an outcome and the day-to-day challenges of research. This will enhance trust and strengthen relationships between the project and stakeholders, including other scientists and decision-makers.

As mentioned above, the Science Explainers are created **through interdisciplinary collaboration**, in which climate scientists work with communication and user engagement experts. This partnership helps to clearly convey their scientific motivations, driving ideas, project progress, and outcomes in a more concrete and accessible manner.

When it comes to the format, the final form of the science explainers will be **factsheets, videos, 1- pagers, or posters** depending on the type of information, which needs to be broken down and disseminated.

Some explainers will be prepared ahead of the Global Annual to Decadal Climate Update (GADCU) by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) to bring the latest project findings about complex interaction between climate drivers, integrated attribution and prediction to GADCU users, such as National Weather Services and decision-makers.

5.1.6 Social media

Social media will be an indispensable part in reaching EXPECT's communication, dissemination, and exploration goals. Therefore, a LinkedIn and a X profile have been created in line with the project's visual identity.

To ensure the LinkedIn and X account remains active, Arctik will regularly create content for social media channels. Furthermore, the communications team will like and repost relevant content from project partners on a weekly basis.

Arctik will regularly contact the project partners to obtain content to share on the project's social media.

As mentioned above, social media templates will be created and shared via Canva, from which Arctik and other project partners will create social media banners with the brand identity of the project.

All social media publications will be related to EXPECT, and the content of new posts should:

- avoid jargon
- have active, personal voice
- be factual rather than opinions

As creating synergies with other projects and events and supporting the exchange of knowledge is incremental to EXPECT, covering relevant events will be part of our social media activities. Consortium members participating in relevant events will be encouraged to post from and about these events and can ask for advice from Arctik.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is particularly appropriate for engaging with leaders in both public and private sectors, and it is also an excellent platform for professionals across all fields, including scientists. Essentially, LinkedIn allows employees and employers to create professional profiles and establish "connections" with one another. This means that any member of the network can invite others to connect professionally.

A dedicated LinkedIn page will be created with the handle @EXPECT Project with the project's logo, visual identity and baseline. This page showcases the project on the platform as an organisation and can be added to consortium members profiles as their workplace.

The LinkedIn format will be used, as a component of the social media strategy, to share project-related content such as articles and more in-depth engagement with the scientific community. We will share and feature content from other stakeholders in the scientific community and actively engage with them to enhance our reach and foster meaningful interactions.

Active consortium members will share posts widely with their networks to boost the visibility of the project.

X

Despite changes in usage patterns since Elon Musk's acquisition (subscription model changes, content moderation policies, algorithm changes), X remains a widely used platform for both business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) communications, which is why the consortium has decided to continue leveraging it for its broad reach and significant audience.

An active X account will be set up in M6 and managed with a monthly calendar. The account will be administered by Arctik with the handle @EXPECT_Project.

The X account will be used to share updates such as:

- news pieces from the website
- upcoming events (both internal and external)
- recently published scientific papers
- video releases.

Arctik will also retweet relevant content from other European research projects and policy communications that are relevant to the EXPECT project.

Social media actions

To build and grow our X and LinkedIn audience, the following actions will be taken:

- To map, follow and like similar accounts to attract follows and engagement.
- Identify and use popular hashtags in relation to the project's area of activity.
- Encourage project partners to use the EXPECT's hashtags as often as possible and repost social media publications published by the project.
- Map partners' X and LinkedIn accounts to follow them from the project account and ask the partners to follow the project's accounts back.
- Encourage project partners participating in relevant events to post about and seek advice from Arctik.
- Repost, like and share the publications of relevant partners on the project's X and LinkedIn accounts.

5.1.7 Policy briefs

In addition to academics and scientists, policy makers will also be targeted with dedicated policy briefs, which, led by BSC and in collaboration with ARCTIK, will be created and distributed at the end of project M12.1 and evaluated in D12.1.

At least one key policy brief will be created at the end of the project, as a part of the science explainers, to summarise and disseminate key findings to policy makers. We aim to go beyond sharing climate information to influence policy decisions. Our intention is to transfer knowledge by understanding the social environment and information flows of the targeted network of policy actors.

Arctik will assist in the dissemination of these policy briefs, ensuring they reach the appropriate stakeholders effectively and efficiently.

5.1.8 Hackathons

Events, both internal and external, will be used to feature the scientific outcomes and technological developments of the project and to boost their dissemination. Within the Task 12.6, Capacity building through Hackathons and an open science platform [M13-48], and led by BSC, two Hackathon-style events of two-three days each will be organised and hosted by the project (M12.3, M12.4).

These Hackathons will gather young academics at the PhD and post-doctoral levels, providing them with the chance to engage with the scientific data and tools developed, and to collaborate with leading scientists in the field during these events. At least, two hackathon events will be held and 30 early-career scientists engaged per event.

The aim of these hackathons is to enhance capacity-building within the climate science community and among young researchers, ensuring the project's impact extends beyond its lifecycle and reaches a broad community of specialists.

These hackathons will focus, in particular, on training related to the Benchmarks developed on ML applications, and on using the tools for efficient analysis of large, distributed data developed within Theme 4: Developing the underpinning infrastructure for efficient processing of large and diverse data.

Joint workshop and final joint event

Along with the organisation of the hackathons, EXPECT plans targeted training events for the wider climate science community, e.g. by contributing to summer schools, online courses and webinars.

To maximise the project's uptake and reach with the target audiences, events will be clustered with other relevant conferences and projects. Relevant networks and the European Commission's sister projects will be reached in that purpose, such as AI4PEX, ASPECT, Impetus4Change, XAIDA and PREVENT Horizon Europe projects.

A joint workshop with relevant projects and initiatives (Month 30) and a final joint event with these projects and initiatives (Month 45) will be held. A summary of the workshop will be published on the project website as part of Task 14.2.; and, under Task 15.2, a detailed summary of the concluding event.

5.2 Multiplier tools and channels

Other ways to collaborate with relevant networks and projects is through agreed presence on each other's websites, inviting representatives from networks and projects to workshops and seminars. We will also aim to be included in newsletters published by sister projects and other multipliers. In addition, we will engage through social media and to maximise the reach of project publications and to foster the dissemination of project outcomes.

Beyond our own channels, the communication and engagement with the audience will take place with external, more established tools and channels. This strategy will enable EXPECT to connect with a broader audience who might not otherwise become aware of the project.

EXPECT has allocated specific resources to coordinate **collaboration with other relevant projects** (Tasks 13.2, 14.2, 15.2), led by BSC, and this will include collaboration with the sister projects funded under the same call.

We will work on **at least five joint activities**, such as workshops, webinars, social media activities, newsletters or news pieces, **to reinforce interactions with relevant research projects**.

In the areas of scientific research, infrastructure development, and communication, dissemination and exploitation, coordination between the sister projects can create a synergistic effect, resulting in outcomes that exceed the sum of their individual contributions. For example, regarding the infrastructure developments, the activities within EXPECT to handle and ingest a variety of distributed data will facilitate the development of other tools (e.g. ESMValTool) that often require local copies of the data in specific formats.

5.2.1 External/public newsletter, blogs, and websites

It has been decided not to publish a dedicated project newsletter; instead, the project will utilise the newsletters of partner institutions, sister projects and other relevant opportunities for communication. The goal will be to maximise the project's reach and disseminate its results to a wide audience.

Additionally, the project will seek to have its results featured on relevant blogs and websites to further extend its reach.

Engagement through external newsletters

Consequently, the engagement strategy will leverage existing newsletters with established networks in our target audience areas. These newsletters will act as EXPECT multipliers.

To achieve this, Arctik will compile a list of pertinent newsletters, both from project partners and external sources. The communications team will approach these newsletters to collaborate on disseminating relevant materials throughout the project. Depending on their reach, certain content and messages will be selectively share to align with the specific interests of each newsletter's audience.

Content to be shared in the newsletter

Here are the types of content EXPECT will provide to external newsletters for inclusion in their publications:

- News from the project (published on the website)
- Promotion of upcoming events
- Summaries of past events
- Recent academic articles or publications
- Videos and other communication materials

5.2.3 Media engagement

To disseminate project outcomes, we will engage with the media. The engagement will depend on the research, outcomes, and relevant target audiences. As

newsworthy outcomes surface throughout the project, press releases will be written to be disseminated to relevant media.

Media mapping

We will map local/regional, national media and European contact points and undertake soft sounding and other communication techniques to maximise the positioning of the project.

A media mapping exercise will be developed in collaboration with WP leaders, which will be gathered under MS12.2. Once we have compiled a list of relevant media outlets, we will start collecting contacts from these sources. Additionally, we can conduct targeted media mapping whenever a new result or project impact needs to be highlighted.

Our goal is to ensure that the media are informed about our project and invited to any relevant workshops or webinars we host. These media interactions will also be assessed in D12.1.

Press releases

To highlight key achievements throughout the project's duration, we will draft and release a series of at least five press releases.

Our aim is to reach out both local and international media to raise awareness of the project and its impacts.

We will encourage partners to share these press releases through their own communication channels and distribute them across relevant media outlets in their respective regions and countries.

5.2.4 Scientific publications

EXPECT will aim to reach at least 20 peer-reviewed publications to disseminate project results to the scientific community, and to inform IPCC and other assessments.

The table below lists examples of scientific publications pertinent to the project and will be continuously updated during the project. These journals have been chosen according to the following criteria:

- Open-access options
- Scientific impact
- Disciplinary and methodological fit

Table 3 – Example of scientific journals for publication

Title of publication
Advances in Climate Change Research
Artificial Intelligence for the Earth Systems
Atmospheric Research

Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society
Climate Dynamics
Climate of the Past
Climate Research
Climatic Change
Communications Earth & Environment
Current Climate Change Reports
Earth's Future
Earth System Dynamics
Environmental Modelling & Software
Environmental Research Letters
Frontiers in Climate
Geophysical Research Letters
Global and Planetary Change
International Journal of Climatology
Journal of Climate
Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres
Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans
Natural Hazards
Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences (NHES)
Nature Climate Change
Nature Communications
PNAS (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)
Regional Environmental Change
Science
Theoretical and Applied Climatology
Weather and Climate Extremes
Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change

5.2.5 External events, conferences, and workshops

The consortium partners will organise and attend events with related stakeholders to disseminate scientific outcomes. Along with the hackathons, the types of events to be organised from within the project include webinars and side-events to larger conferences.

Events, such as webinars and conferences will be key to disseminating the scientific outcomes of the project and form T12.2. EXPECT will be present in at least **three webinars**, with the objective to disseminate key findings and engage experts and target audiences such as the scientific community and policymakers.

To maximise their uptake and reach with the target audiences, we will cluster events with other relevant conferences and projects, particularly the sister projects. This cross-project collaboration will be facilitated through various interactions, including joint workshops and webinars, as well as coordinated efforts on social media, newsletters, and news articles.

The EXPECT project will collaborate with and complement its sister projects, including the AI4PEX Horizon Europe initiative. While there are no critical dependencies between the two, we have actively engaged in discussions with the AI4PEX consortium to identify potential areas for collaboration and have encouraged our partners to participate in these joint efforts.

Examples of external events and cross-project collaboration

The Explaining and Predicting Earth System Change **Webinar series** (an initiative by the EPESC-LHA) will be a suitable medium to reach large parts of the interested climate science community.

Synergies to help with the efficient dissemination and exploitation in terms of training activities will also include contributions to **online courses** (e.g. the MOOC on ML in Weather & Climate organised by ECMWF) and **summer schools** (e.g. the NCAS Climate Modelling Summer School).

5.3. EC tools and channels

We will explore all relevant opportunities to communicate and disseminate the project's activities and results through EC and Horizon Europe communication channels, including social media, to enhance the project's visibility and engage a broader audience. The project coordinator will keep in regular contact with the Project Officer, updating them on noteworthy news, results, or events.

Additionally, we will consider utilising various tools and channels provided by the European Commission for Horizon Europe projects, such as:

Table 4 – EC tools and channels

Type of channel	Name
Publications	Newsletters
	Horizon Magazine
	Open Research Europe Research*eu - magazine
Audio-visual	Futuris Magazine – Euro News
Online News	ECs Research and Innovation website

6 Content strategy

6.1 Content calendar

The planning of communications activities and campaigns will be organised using **an editorial and a social media calendar** based on the marketing funnel model, which is outlined in section 3.2, Engagement Triangle.

This calendar will help track the progress of communication efforts and ensure that we meet our target KPIs. It will be used to manage all types of content, including social media, newsletters, events, videos, news, articles/blogs, and deliverables, and will be hosted on the project's Wiki.

The content calendar is considered a living document that will be revised and updated throughout the project. The calendar will be updated as a part of WP12.

6.1.1 Editorial content

As mentioned above, editorial content produced for EXPECT's website will follow the Know – Like – Trust approach, laid out in section [Error! Reference source not found.](#), allowing the different audiences to get familiar with the project and its output, grow fond of it and trust its research. We will make sure to use a language that is easily understood by people of various professional backgrounds.

6.2 Communications and marketing campaigns

The project's LinkedIn and X accounts will run campaigns throughout its duration to direct the target audiences to the project website.

This will be achieved by linking posts to news articles or specific sections on the website. The project will also use images, videos, and GIFs to ensure the posts are eye-catching and maintain the project's visual identity.

Internal reports, along with the periodic project reports at M18 and M36, will compile and evaluate the impact of all communication activities, including those outlined in D12.1.

In the first year of the project, as the EXPECT project is setting up its research areas and gathering data, the primary focus will be on raising awareness about the project. Therefore, we will assess how the different involved stakeholders can benefit from and what methodologies are applied.

The table below provides an overview of the objectives, messages, tools, and channels for this initial campaign.

Table 5 – Campaign 1, What is EXPECT?

Campaign 1 – What is EXPECT	
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of the project • Launch the website • Launch the social media profiles • Increase followers on LinkedIn and X
Messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is EXPECT? • What can EXPECT do for you? • Why is the research done under EXPECT important? • Why do assessments and predictions of regional climate change matter? • What solutions are we aiming to find? • Who are the people behind EXPECT?
Tools and channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media: LinkedIn and X • Website • Video • Blogposts/articles/interviews • External newsletters

Other campaigns will be defined at a later stage when the outcomes of the results will be better known. Examples for potential campaigns include:

- Campaign to disseminate specific research results
- Campaign to disseminate specific events
- Campaigns to promote the science explainers
- Campaign to advertise the first Hackathon
- Campaign to advertise the second Hackathon
- Campaign to promote the launch of the EXPECT open science platform
- Campaigns to promote products and services

7 Monitoring and evaluation

Performing an evaluation is necessary to analyse the effectiveness of the actions taken and to optimise future actions. The communication and dissemination activities of EXPECT will be regularly monitored and assessed through the set Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and other indicators.

7.1 Communication KPIs

The KPIs are set based on our previous experience with H2020/Horizon Europe projects, as well as on the described strategy. The KPIs detailed in the table below were set considering the use of tools as described in section [Error! Reference source not found.](#) to reach communication goals. These goals will be re-evaluated with every update of the CDP to determine where efforts need to be adjusted.

Table 6 – EXPECT communication KPIs

Dissemination activity	Methodology	KPI	Target (end of project M48)
Project website	Google analytics	Number of total visits	7.200
LinkedIn (social media)	LinkedIn analytics	Followers	800
		Campaigns	5
		Avg. impressions (reach) per post (non-sponsored)	100-200
		Avg. impressions (reach) per post (sponsored)	300-700
		Avg. engagements (like retweet, comments) per tweet (sponsored)	2% - 4% 4.00% video view rate
		Avg. engagements (like retweet, comments) per tweet (sponsored)	3% - 5% 4.00% video view rate
X (social media)	X analytics	Followers	600
		Campaigns	5
		Avg. impressions (reach) per tweet (non-sponsored)	50-150

		Avg. impressions (reach) per tweet (sponsored)	200-500
		Avg. engagements (like retweet, comments) per tweet (non-sponsored)	1% - 3% 4.00% video view rate
		Avg. engagements (like retweet, comments) per tweet (sponsored)	2% - 4% 5.00% video view rate
Media	Communication activity reporting	Articles/press releases published on EXPECT channels	40
		Articles/press releases published on external channels	5
Events	Communication activity reporting	Expect organised events	6
		Total participants at Expect organised events	200
		External events attended by EXPECT partners	15
		External events showcased on the EXPECT website	10
Publications	Communication activity reporting	Publications published in journals/magazines	20
Science explainers	Communication activity reporting	Informative sheets on key concepts and topics of the project to educate, and facilitate understanding of results	5
Visuals including communication materials and videos	Communication activity reporting	Videos	5
	Communication activity reporting	Flyers	1

7.2 Challenges and opportunities

As challenges often occur during the implementation of a communications plan, we have identified some important challenges and present them with solutions.

Table 7 - Challenges and proposed solutions

<p>Challenge: Simplifying complex topics for effective communication.</p> <p>Solution: Use clear and straightforward language to outline the project's overall goal through storytelling. Incorporate examples and specify tangible socio-economic impacts within the narratives.</p>
<p>Challenge: Managing a diverse range of partners and stakeholders.</p> <p>Solution: Enhance communication and coordination of promotional activities among all parties. The project will delegate communication responsibilities to partners while maintaining oversight of the messages produced.</p>
<p>Challenge: Addressing various target groups with differing languages and professional vocabularies.</p> <p>Solution: Tailor messages to suit the specific needs of each audience.</p>
<p>Challenge: Communication often gets overlooked during research and technology discussions, leading to partners neglecting communication efforts.</p> <p>Solution: Maintain a strong focus on communication activities relevant to project deliverables. Implement regular monthly reminders asking, "Is there anything to communicate?". Provide coordinated support and schedule regular bilateral meetings every two months or as necessary. Establish a specific communication activity upon reaching scientific milestones.</p>

7.3 Reporting

An annual report will be written by Arctik to showcase past activities, and the milestones reached for communication, dissemination, and exploitation. The annual report will be shared in months 12, 24, 36 and 48.

7.3.1 Communication activities reporting

The main objective of this reporting is to have a comprehensive overview of the places and audiences reached by EXPECT initiatives to be able to assess the scope of these efforts on one hand and on the other hand to evaluate the pertinence with the communications strategy and its objectives.

Each institution is responsible for reporting their activities. However, to simplify the process Arctik has prepared guidelines on how to use the Horizon portal for reporting.

Appendix A – Stakeholders mapping

Name	Website	Audience type
AI4PEX Horizon Europe project	https://ai4pex.org/	Sister projects
ASPECT Horizon Europe project	https://www.aspect-project.eu	Sister projects
I4C Horizon Europe project	https://impetus4change.eu	Sister projects
XAIDA	https://xaida.eu/	Sister projects
PREVENT		Sister projects
EERIE	https://eerie-project.eu	Sister projects
OptimESM	https://optimesm-he.eu	Sister projects
The Conversation	https://theconversation.com	Media
Carbon Brief	https://www.carbonbrief.org/	Media
GSCC Network	https://gscnetwork.org	Media
WCRP EPESC Lighthouse Activity	https://www.wcrp-climate.org/epesc	Climate scientists
CMIP IPO	https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip7/	Climate scientists
European Environmental Agency		Policymakers
IPCC, WG 1	https://www.ipcc.ch/working-group/wg1/	
WMO Lead Center for Annual to Decadal prediction	https://hadleyserver.metoffice.gov.uk/wmo/olc/	Others
CINEA	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/index_en	Others
ESIWACE	https://www.esiwace.eu	Others
Destination Earth	https://destine.ecmwf.int	Others
nextGEMS	https://nextgems-h2020.eu	Others
Space4Climate	https://space4climate.com/	Others
Copernicus	https://climate.copernicus.eu	Others
GSCC Network	https://gscnetwork.org/	Others

Appendix B – Draft content calendar, 2024-2025

2024

Month	Channel	Type	Title	Consortium Member
October	Website	News	Launch of the website (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik
October	Social media	Link	Launch of the website (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik
October	Website	News	What is EXPECT? What can EXPECT do for you? (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	All
October	Social media	Link	What is EXPECT? What can EXPECT do for you? (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / All
October	Website	Milestone	MS3.1 Workshop on methods to assess drivers of annual to decadal changes in climate Summary published on website (T3.1) - Month 6	MO
October	Social media	Link	Promo – MS3.1 Workshop on methods to assess drivers of annual to decadal changes in climate	Arctik / MO
November	Website	News	What solutions is EXPECT aiming to find? / EXPECT goals (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	All
November	Social media	Link	What solutions is EXPECT aiming to find? / EXPECT goals (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / All
November	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: World Science Day for Peace and Development (10 Nov)	Arctik
November	Website	News	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 1 (WP1). T1.1 Bridging different types of data (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	DKRZ

November	Social media	Link	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 1 (WP1). T1.1 Bridging different types of data (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / DKRZ
November	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP1 / WP7) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	DKRZ
November	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP1 / WP7) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / DKRZ
December	Website	News	Promo – Methodology – Theme 1 (WP1 / WP2)	DKRZ / ECMWF
December	Social media	Link	Promo – Methodology – Theme 1 (WP1 / WP2)	Arctik / DKRZ / ECMWF
December	Website	News	Report summary from the first General Assembly	All
December	Social media	Link	Report summary from the first General Assembly	Arctik / All
December	Website	News	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 2 (WP3) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	VUA
December	Social media	Link	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 2 (WP3). T3.1 Drivers of annual to decadal changes (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / VUA

2025

Month	Channel	Type	Title	Consortium Member
January	Website	News	What have you been reading / What will you be reading during the holidays	All
January	Social media	Link	What have you been reading / What will you be reading during the holidays	Arctik / All
January	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP1) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	DKRZ
January	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP1) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik / DKRZ
January	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: International Day of Education (24 Jan)	Arctik
January	Website	News	Promo – Methodology – Theme 2 (WP3 / WP4)	VUA / MO
January	Social media	Link	Promo – Methodology – Theme 2 (WP3 / WP4)	Arctik / VUA / MO
February	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: World Wetlands Day (02 Feb) OR International Day of Women & Girls in Science (11 Feb)	Arctik
February	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP2) T3.1 Drivers of annual to decadal changes <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	ECMWF

February	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP2) T3.1 Drivers of annual to decadal changes (<i>Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?</i>)	Arctik / ECMWF
February	Website	News	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 3 (WP5) T5.1. Diagnostics for the role of large-scale circulation (<i>Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?</i>)	ECMWF
February	Social media	Link	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 3 (WP5) T5.1. Diagnostics for the role of large-scale circulation (<i>Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?</i>)	Arctik / ECMWF
March	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP3) (<i>Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?</i>)	VUA
March	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP3) (<i>Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?</i>)	Arctik / VUA
March	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: World Meteorological Day (23 Mar)	Arctik
March	Website	News	Promo – Methodology – Theme 3 (WP5 / WP6)	ECMWF / BSC
March	Social media	Link	Promo – Methodology – Theme 3 (WP5 / WP6)	Arctik / ECMWF / BSC
April	Website	News	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 4 (WP7). T7.1 Infrastrucrure fundamentals	DKRZ

			<i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	
April	Social media	Link	Why is the research done under EXPECT important? – Theme 4 (WP7). T7.1 Infrastructure fundamentals <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik / DKRZ
April	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: International Mother Earth Day (22 Apr)	Arctik
April	Website	News	Introductory video <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik
April	Social media	Link	Promo Introductory video <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik
May	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP4) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	MO
May	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP4) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik / MO
May	Website	News	Coverage of the GA2	All
May	Social media	Link	Coverage of the GA2	Arctik / All
May	Website	News	Summary of the first year of the project	All
May	Social media	Link	Summary of the first year of the project	Arctik / All
May	Website	News	Promo – Methodology – Theme 4 (WP7 / WP8 / WP9)	DKRZ / UREAD / CINECA
May	Social media	Link	Promo – Methodology – Theme 4 (WP7 / WP8 / WP9)	DKRZ / UREAD / CINECA

June	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: World Environment Day (05 Jun)	Arctik
June	Website	Flyer	Flyer of the project (MS11.2) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik
June	Social media	Link	Promo - Flyer of the project (MS11.2) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik
June	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP6 / WP10 / WP13 / WP14 / WP15) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	BSC
June	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP6 / WP10 / WP13 / WP14 / WP15) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / BSC
June	Website	News	What have you been reading / What will you be reading during the summer	All
June	Social media	Link	What have you been reading / What will you be reading during the summer	Arctik / All
July	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP8) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	UREAD
July	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP8) (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik / UREAD
July	Social media	Link	Promo Introductory video (Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)	Arctik
August	Website	Flyer	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP9)	CINECA

			<i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	
August	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP9) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik / CINECA
August	Social media	Link	Promo - Flyer of the project (MS11.2)	Arctik
September	Social media	Link	Top-topical communication - Hook: International Day of Clean Air for Blue Skies (07 Sep) OR International Day for the Preservation of the Ozone Layer (16 Sep)	Arctik
September	Website	News	Article: Climate extreme events during summer 2025	
September	Social media	Link	Promo article - Climate extreme events during summer 2025	
September	Website	News	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP11) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik
September	Social media	Link	Who are the people behind EXPECT? (WP12) <i>(Campaign 1: What is EXPECT?)</i>	Arctik

Appendix C – Guidelines for Reporting Communications and Disseminations Activities

Step 1 Go to **the portal** and sign in with your **personal login** and **password**.

ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home

The screenshot shows the EU Funding & Tenders Portal home page. A hand cursor icon is positioned over the 'Sign in' button in the top right corner. The page features a navigation menu, a main banner with various project images, and sections for 'Discover the funding & tenders opportunities', 'Find calls for proposals', 'Find calls for tenders', 'View projects and results', and 'Work as an expert'.

Step 2 Go to **My projects** on the left-hand side.

The screenshot shows the EU Funding & Tenders Portal with the 'My Projects' menu item highlighted on the left-hand side. A hand cursor icon is positioned over the 'My Projects' link. The page layout is similar to the previous screenshot, but the focus is on the user's personal navigation options.

Step 3 Find **Expect** and click on **Actions – Manage project.**

Step 4 You will get this screen. Select **Continuous Reporting.**

Step 5

A new **pop-up window** will open.

a

→ If you want to report a **dissemination activity**, click on the **Dissemination Activities** tab.

or

b

→ If you want to report a **communications activity**, click on the **Communications Activities** tab.

Dissemination activities

Click on **Add Dissemination Activity** on the top right-hand side of the screen.

Fill in all the fields and click on **Add**.

Click on **Save** on the top right-hand corner of the page.

We suggest to report only on delivered activities.

Communication activities

Click on **Add Communication Activity** on the top right-hand side of the page.

Fill in all the fields. In the outcome field, include related specific **key performance indicators**.

Click **ok**.

Click on **Save** on the top right-hand corner of the page.

